

ENHANCEMENT OF STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS OF CLAYEY SOIL USING CEMENT-FLY ASH AND GEOGRID

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Abstract

The properties of the soil subgrade have a significant impact on how well a pavement performs. The soil must have good physical and geotechnical properties to be able to sustain the load and transfer it to the ground. The soil that is used in this study is identified as clayey soil. When wet, clayey soil becomes stickier and when it's dry, it develops surface fracture. The engineering properties of the soil can be enhanced by using additives. In this study, fly ash is added to the soil in varying amounts (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%) along with 5% of cement to determine the most ideal fly ash amount that will increase the soil's strength. Geogrid is then placed at various depths H/4, H/2, and 3H/4 from the top of the soil to determine the ideal geogrid placement depth that will increase the soil's strength the most as measured by the CBR value. Atterberg limits, Proctor compaction test, unconfined compression strength, and CBR test are the tests used in this study. According to the experiment findings, adding fly ash and cement admixtures caused the soil's plasticity to decrease, and MDD to rise with a decrease in OMC. Soil that had 10% fly ash and 5% cement showed the highest value of CBR, increasing 7.50 times that of untreated soil and having a UCC strength of 194.77 kPa.

Keywords: Soil Stabilization, Cement, Fly Ash, Geosynthetic, Geogrid

1. INTRODUCTION

The stability of a structure is determined by the underlying soil's stability. When in contact with water, weak subgrades of clayey soil have a strong tendency to swell and shrink. It is common for clayey soil to exhibit poor engineering features like inadequate bearing capacity, major shrinkage and swell, and high moisture susceptibility. It is common to stabilize this soil to increase its tensile strength [1]. In order to be used as structural support, fine-grained soils with high plasticity must first have their engineering characteristics significantly and economically improved. The strength of the soil can be improved by using additives [2], [3], [4]. These additives come in a variety of forms, from manufactured materials to waste products like fly ash, cement, lime, etc. For engineering as well as construction factors, soil stabilization is a method of improving the properties of soil and it can be a very useful material for construction in many countries [5],[6]. To improve the qualities of the problematic soil, soil stabilization is accomplished by blending and mixing the stabilizer material with it [7]. The method is typically separated into the categories of mechanical stabilization and chemical stabilization. Fly ash is a waste product created during the energy production process in thermal power plants from the burning of coal that pollutes the environment [8]. In order to reduce air pollution, the pollution control department has implemented rules and regulations since the FA's disposal causes an alarming environmental risk [9]. In the current study, FA was added to subgrade soil in varied quantities to increase the soil's strength, resulting in more affordable

and environmentally friendly construction. The use of fly ash for soil stabilization has proven to be quite effective in raising the strength qualities of soils in numerous structural projects. According to [10], the CBR value increased by 27% when FA was added compared to virgin soil. [1] Discovered that soil with 18% FA raised CBR value by roughly 2.55 times that of the control specimen and demonstrated the maximum increase in UCC strength of 156.19 kPa. Ref [11] discovered that adding 20% fly ash to the stabilized soil caused a 50% decrease in the plasticity index and swelling properties. It is more efficient to use cement and fly ash stabilizers rather than only fly ash. The majority of fly ash is a secondary binder, which cannot generate the required result on its own but can react chemically in the presence of a small amount of activation to create cementitious compounds that can strengthen the strength of soft soil [12]. Through a series of unconfined compressive strength and physical tests, the possibility and effectiveness of incorporating fly ash into cement-admixed clay were investigated. From numerous experiments, it has been confirmed that, with the right amount of cement, fly ash may successfully be added to soil cement to improve both strength and physical features [13]–[15]. Since soil stabilization technology was developed in the 1960s, cement has been used as a binding agent [16], [17]. The amount of cement often used is small but sufficient to enhance the soil's engineering qualities and the cation exchange of the clay. The quality of the soil can be changed and improved, or the soil can be turned into a cemented mass with greater strength and durability by using cement [14], [18], [19]. In fact, cement stabilization offers an efficient solution to the issue of fatigue failures brought on by recurrent excessive deflection of asphalt surfaces where a weak subgrade occurs in the pavement structure [20], [21]. Ref [2] Because of the pozzolanic reaction created by the addition of cement and fly ash, it was noticed that the value of UCC raised as the curing time increased, demonstrating the effectiveness of utilizing cement to stabilize soil with fly ash. As it was found that adding 15% fly ash and 5% cement to the soil increased its strength and durability and decreased its swelling and plasticity properties. With a higher percentage of fly ash mixed with 5% cement, the swelling potential and swell pressure values decreased from 18.7 to 4.5% and from 175 to 75 kPa. Similarly, According to [22], which investigated the stabilization of clay soil using fly ash and cement, the ratio of 5% cement to 15% fly ash enhanced the clay's engineering qualities and also helped increase its bearing capacity. Ref [23] investigated the effect of engineering properties of soil by the inclusion of recycled polyethylene terephthalate (PET) fibers in combination with the fly ash in the subgrade soil. They showed an improvement in the shear strength, California Bearing Ratio (CBR) value, and a decrease in the plasticity index for clayey soils

Since the 1970s, when the soil is weak because of its low consistency and excessive compressibility, geogrid has been utilized to reinforce the subgrade and subbase during the development of unpaved roads and places [24],[25], [26] [25]. In almost every case, the settlement was found to be reduced by 20% as a result of the addition of geosynthetic layers, demonstrating the efficiency of the reinforcement [27]–[29]. Among these, geogrid is mostly utilized for reinforcing work to stabilize and strengthen the subgrade soil during the construction of roads. Geogrid was used to study the engineering performance of various soil types, and it was discovered that both in the laboratory and in the field, the CBR value increases in reinforced cases compared to the unreinforced case [30]–[32]31]. Ref [33] studying the usage of anchored geogrid in weak subgrade soil to increase CBR value brought researchers to the conclusion that the anchored reinforcement produced greater CBR values than unreinforced soil. Ref [34] They carried out experimental studies to increase the soil's strength by stabilizing

it with fly ash and reinforcing it with geonet, and they discovered that the soil with the highest CBR value was stabilized with 18% of fly ash reinforced with geogrid and placed 3H/4 depth from the top. Ref [35] discovered that employing geogrid can enhance the performance of soils under soaking conditions. There are many researchers who found out that implying geogrid more than one layer gives more strength than single-layer reinforcement. Ref [36] stated that increasing from one to two reinforcement layers gave the best outcome in terms of the composite materials' bearing ratio.

2. MATERIALS

2.1 Soil sample

The soil sample used in this study is classified as clayey soil. The soil was obtained from a construction site located at Khanpur, Punjab. Numerous tests were conducted to determine the engineering properties of the soil as per IS 2720 and the results are recorded in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of soil

Properties	Values
Specific gravity	2.60
Clay%	56%
Silt%	20%
Sand%	56%
Liquid limit	44.25
Plastic limit	20.91
Plasticity index	23.34
Soil classification	CL
CBR %	4.82

2.2 Fly ash

Fly ash is a heterogeneous by-product of the coal combustion process utilized in power plants. Fly ash contains pozzolanic elements, which combine with cement to create cementitious compounds. Fly ash is divided into two primary categories: class C and class F. Class C fly ash is created by burning sub-bituminous coal. Because of the high amount of free CaO, it has excellent cement characteristics. Anthracite and bituminous coal are burned to produce Class F fly ash. It has weak self-cementing characteristics. The fly ash that is used in this study is class C fly ash and it was obtained from Khanpur.

2.3 Cement

Due to its accessibility and general ability to be applied to a variety of materials, cement is one of the most widely used soil stabilizers. Because it can be used alone to achieve the required stabilizing action, it may be regarded as the principal stabilizing agent in a hydraulic binder. There are numerous varieties of cement available on the market, including regular Portland cement, blast furnace cement, sulfate-resistant cement, and high alumina cement.

2.4 Geogrid

Among the various forms of geogrids, biaxial polypropylene geogrid is chosen for the present study, whose properties are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Geogrid properties

Material	Size and type
Geogrid	Biaxial
Aperture size	12*12
Density	1.13g/cm ³
Rib thickness	2mm
Area with mass per unit	0.1g/cm ³
Tensile strength	100 (KN/m)

Figure 8: Geogrid

Figure 9: Fly ash

Figure 9: Soil

3. METHODOLOGY

As admixtures, fly ash and cement compound are mixed with the soil to stabilize it. To ascertain their impact on the engineering qualities of soil, several percentages of fly ash—5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%—were examined. The cement concentration remained fixed at 5%. Experiments were conducted to determine the Atterberg limits, Standard Proctor compaction values, CBR values, and unconfined compression strength for various combinations of samples in order to analyse the effects of their replacement. A soaked CBR test was conducted to determine the ideal depth of geogrid placement which will give the maximum value in the CBR test, geogrid is placed at different depths at different depths of the soil (H/4, H/3, 3H/4) from the top of the soil specimen.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from the tests such as the Atterberg limit, proctor compaction test, and unconfined compressive strength test are listed below and the results of the CBR test conducted on soil with varying percentages of fly ash cement stabilization and on soil reinforced with geogrid are tabulated below:

4.1 Soil consistency

Figure 1 shows the variance in clayey soil treated with cement fly ash in terms of soil consistency qualities like liquid limit and plasticity index. From this figure, it is evident that the plasticity index gradually decreases with increasing fly ash percentage (with constant

cement of 5%), and the plastic limit values increase with the addition of cement fly ash (as indicated in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Cement-fly ash's impact on soil consistency

4.2 Compaction Characteristics

Figure 2 and figure 3 show the compaction characteristics for soil samples stabilized with cement-fly ash as described by maximum dry density and optimum moisture content. According to these figures and tables, MDD peak values are at 5% cement and 10% fly ash. It is observed that with increasing percentages of cement fly ash, the OMC of the soil starts to decrease while the MDD of the soil increased (table 3). These findings show that cement fly ash addition considerably impacts compaction properties.

Table 3: OMC and MDD for soil sample with variable percentages of cement-fly ash

Soil sample	MDD (gm/cm ³)	OMC%
CS (soil+ 0% cement+ 0% fly ash)	1.59	21.5
Soil + 5% cement +5% fly ash	1.62	16
Soil + 5% cement + 10% fly ash	2.115	12
Soil + 5% cement + 15% fly ash)	1.76	19.28
Soil + 5% cement + 20% fly ash)	2	13.46

Figure 2: Cement-fly ash's impact on soil optimum moisture content

Figure 3: Cement-fly ash's impact on soil's maximum dry density

4.3 Unconfined compressive strength

UCC test was conducted on clayey soil with varying percentages of fly ash and cement to determine the shear strength of the soil. Table 4 & figure 4 shows the result of the UCC strength test. Figure 4 depicts the impact of fly ash and cement on enhancing the stability of the stabilized soil using various fly ash percentages and 5% cement. The UCC strength results indicate that the addition of cement fly ash causes a gradual increase in compressive stress.

Table 4: UCC strength of cement-fly ash soil

Soil sample	UCC strength(kPa)
CS (soil+ 0% cement+ 0% fly ash)	180.21
Soil + 5% cement +5% fly ash	174.21
Soil + 5% cement + 10% fly ash	194.77
Soil + 5% cement + 15% fly ash)	186.45
Soil + 5% cement + 20% fly ash)	188.38

Figure 4: Cement-fly ash's impact on soil's unconfined compressive strength

4.4 Soaked CBR test with variable content of FA

Figure 5 & table 5 shows the variation of the soil's soaked CBR after being stabilized by cement fly ash. It is apparent from this graph that the soil exhibits a significant increase in CBR when cement-fly ash additives are added. Peak CBR values are observed at 10% and 15% of fly ash. After the soil stabilized at 15% fly ash and above, the CBR values started to decline.

Table 5: CBR value of soil with variable percentages of cement fly ash

Soil sample	CBR value %
CS (soil+ 0% cement+ 0% fly ash)	4.82
Soil + 5% cement +5% fly ash	22.16
Soil + 5% cement + 10% fly ash	36.24
Soil + 5% cement + 15% fly ash)	33
Soil + 5% cement + 20% fly ash)	21

4.5 Soaked CBR test on soil sample with geogrid placed at different depths

By splitting the heights of the CBR mould into four heights at H/4, H/3, and 3H/4 from the top, a soil specimen with geogrid set at various depths was created. It was observed from the results that in the case of clayey soil as the depth of placement of geogrid was increased from H/4 to 3H/4. The CBR value was found to be increased from 4.82 to 15.14 for soil with geogrid placed at 3H/4 depth (Figure6). It increases about 3.15 times the CBR of untreated clayey soil. The values is shown on table 6.

Table 6: Soaked CBR values for the soil sample with Geogrid placed at varying depths

Soil sample	CBR value%
CS (without geogrid)	4.82
H/4	10.82
H/2	13.68
3H/4	15.14

Table 7: Soaked CBR values for the soil with ideal percentage of FA with Geogrid placed at optimum depth

Soil sample	CBR value %
CS (10% FA & without geogrid)	36.24
H/4	37.96
H/2	39
3H/4	42.26

Figure 5: Cement-fly ash's impact on soil's CBR

Figure 6: Soaked CBR values for the soil sample with geogrid placed at varying depths

In the case where geogrid is positioned at various depths and soil is mixed with 10% FA. Geogrid placed at 3H/4 gained a maximum increase of 42.26 (as shown in figure 7 and table 7) which is 2.80 times the soil with geogrid placed at 3H/4 and 1.16 times the clayey soil stabilized with 10% of FA and 5% of cement. Thus, it can be concluded that adding geogrid at a depth of 3H/4 from the top to soil that has been strengthened with 10% FA is the ideal admixture.

Figure 7: Soaked CBR values for the soil sample stabilized with 10% fly ash and 5% cement with geogrid placed at varying depths

5. CONCLUSION

The experimental findings show the positive impacts of geogrid reinforcement and cement fly ash stabilization. Based on the results, fly ash mixed with cement is an effective soil stabilization agent. In this study, fly ash was used to stabilize clayey soil at varying rates of 5, 10, 15, and 20 percent combined with a fixed cement ratio of 5 percent. As the amount of fly ash plus 5% cement increased, it was found that the soil's MDD increased while the OMC decreased. It was found that 10% FA addition with 5 cement produced the most effective results, with maximum UCC strength of about 194.77 kPa and a maximum soaked CBR value of around 36.24%. The ideal depth placement of geogrid was found to be at 3H/4 depth from the soil which gives a CBR value of 15.14%. The stabilizing soil with 10% FA and 5% cement was discovered to be more effective than clayey soil reinforced with geogrid placed at 3H/4 depth from the top of the soil. The CBR value of soil stabilized with 10% FA and 5% cement with geogrid placed at 3H/4 depth from the top of the soil is 42.26%, which is 2.79 times more than the value of soil reinforced with geogrid alone at the same depth and 1.16 times greater than the value of soil stabilized with 10% FA. Hence, 5% of cement and 10% of cement can be effectively used in soil stabilization with reinforcement of geogrid by placing at 3H/4 depth from the soil specimen.

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